

Synthesis and Amoebicidal Activity of Some 2-Methyl-6(8)-alkyl-4-(arylsulphonylhydrazino)quinolines

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A series of substituted 4-(arylsulphonylhydrazino)quinolines have been synthesised for studying their amoebicidal activity. All the compounds were screened for amoebicidal activity against *E. histolytica*. Contrary to expectations, no significant amoebicidal activity was observed when testing was done against the axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 125 µg/ml.

A large number of quinoline derivatives like vioform (5-chloro, 7-iodo, 8-hydroxy quinoline), chloroquin and intestopan are well known amoebicides^{1,2,3}. Recently, some 4-substituted quinoline derivatives showed enhanced activity against *E. coli*^{4,5}. Many substituted sulphonamides also exhibited potent amoebicidal activity⁶⁻¹¹. It seemed, therefore, of interest to synthesise the title compounds with the object of ascertaining whether the presence of a sulphonyl moiety in quinolines could augment their amoebicidal activity.

Substituted-4-chloroquinolines were refluxed with *p*-substituted arylsulphonylhydrazides in ethanol for 10 hr to furnish the desired quinolines.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in sulphuric acid bath in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-137 spectrometer in KBr.

Substituted-4-chloroquinolines^{1,2} and *p*-substituted arylsulphonylhydrazides¹²⁻¹⁶ were synthesised by reported method.

4-(Arylsulphonylhydrazino)quinolines: A mixture of substituted 4-chloroquinoline (0.01 mole) and *p*-substituted arylsulphonylhydrazide (0.01 mole) was refluxed in 50 ml of absolute ethanol for 10 hr. The resulting mixture was concentrated and allowed to stand overnight.

The crystals which separated were filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The yield ranged between 45 to 65%.

The structure of the compounds was confirmed by their ir spectra. The compounds showed a broad band in the region 3200-2700 cm⁻¹ characteristic for -NH- and -CH stretching. The ring stretching bands (skeletal bands) occur in the region between 1630-1420 cm⁻¹. Two bands at 1350-1325 cm⁻¹ and 1160-1155 cm⁻¹ showed the presence of -SO₂NH-group in the molecule. The properties of the compounds thus obtained are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—2-METHYL-6(8)-ALKYL-4-(ARYLSULPHONYLHYDRAZINO)QUINOLINES*

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	232
2.	H	CH ₃	218
3.	H	OCH ₃	200
4.	H	NHCOCH ₃	192
5.	8-CH ₃	H	178
6.	8-CH ₃	CH ₃	202
7.	8-CH ₃	OCH ₃	188
8.	8-CH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	213
9.	6-CH ₃	H	184
10.	6-CH ₃	CH ₃	198
11.	6-CH ₃	OCH ₃	190
12.	6-CH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	175
13.	8-OCH ₃	H	141
14.	8-OCH ₃	CH ₃	128
15.	8-OCH ₃	OCH ₃	172
16.	8-OCH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	195
17.	6-OCH ₃	H	192
18.	6-OCH ₃	CH ₃	206
19.	6-OCH ₃	OCH ₃	220
20.	6-OCH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	204

* All the compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C, H, N and S.

Amoebicidal activity: The test compound was dissolved in dimethyl formamide and then diluted with water. It was sterilized by autoclaving for 15 min. Axenic culture of *E. histolytica* (strain 200 :

NIH) was maintained in modified TPS-1 medium containing 0.2% cystine in screw capped tubes at pH 6.8. 10000 amoebae/ml of the culture medium, as determined by leuckocytometer count, were inoculated at the bottom of tubes and the tubes were incubated at 37°. Three days old amoeba cultures were used in the experiments described below.

1 ml of a test solution was added to 8 ml of the modified TPS—1 medium in a screw capped tube and incubated overnight. 1 ml of inoculum, containing 10000 amoebae was then added to the bottom of the tube. The tubes were incubated at 37° and amoebicidal end point was determined during 72 hr under an inverted microscope.

In doubtful cases, subcultures were made. In a set of experiments, tubes in duplicates at each dilution of a compound and two controls were included. The standard drugs used were emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole (Flagyl). Unfortunately none of the compounds showed any significant activity at concentration of 125 mg/ml against *E. histolytica*.

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References

1. A. U. DEY and B. PATHAK, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 152.
2. J. H. OSBOND, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1853.
3. MESSER, N. MAYER Ger. Patent, 1, 296, 635, Sept. 18, 1969; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 124276.
4. V. S. MISRA and V. K. SAXENA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1972, **314**, 5, 958.
5. S. E. HAWKINS and J. M. HAINTON, *Microbiol.*, 1972, **5**, 57.
6. Y. NAGANO and M. MURAKAMI, Japan Patent, 7326, 771, Apr. 9, 1973; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **78**, 159470.
7. V. K. AGARWAL, K. C. SAH, S. NAGAR and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1971, **312**, 964.
8. R. D. DESAI, G. S. SAHARIA and H. S. SODHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 411.
9. N. A. SIMMONS, *J. Clin. Path.*, 1970, **23**, 754.
10. C. ALBERTI and C. TIRONO *Farmaco. Ed. Sci.*, 1967, **22**, 418; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **67**, 32640.
11. V. S. MISRA and V. K. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 967.
12. V. K. MEHTA, D. R. PATEL and R. S. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 633.
13. L. CURTIUS, *J. Prakt. Chemie*, 1898, **58**, 166.
14. A. ALBERTI and R. ROYER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1148.
15. A. L. MANDZHAYAN, A. S. AKANYANARD and A. D. ANOYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh. (USSR)*, 1969, **22**, 488; *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **72**, 21667.
16. J. S. ROTH and E. F. DEGERING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 126.